

The Critical Consideration of Generation Z Acceptance of The Facial Recognition Technology Future Implementation in the Front Office Department of a Family-Owned Car Rental Company in Bali

Ni Putu Ina Trhisnawati Weca

Swiss Hotel Management School, University of Derby

ABSTRACT: This study explores the acceptance of AI in Facial Recognition Technology among Generation Z in the front office department of a family-owned car rental company in Bali. By employing a mixed-methods approach, the study investigates the potential benefits and challenges of implementing this technology, its impact on customer experience, and its role in optimizing business operations. The study utilizes three frameworks, including the Technology Acceptance Model, Balance Scorecard, Hoshin Planning Kanri, and Business Model Canvas, to provide insights into the current behaviors and attitudes of Generation Z consumers towards facial recognition technology. The findings suggest that while there is a moderate level of interest in the implementation of AI technology, there is also a significant financial investment required for small family-owned businesses. Thus, the study provides recommendations for family-owned car rental businesses to carefully weigh the potential benefits and costs of implementing facial recognition technology while meeting the expectations of their customers.

KEYWORDS: Business operations, customer experience, generation Z, facial recognition technology

INTRODUCTION

As cutting-edge end-user technology has continually made its way into the hospitality industry, services have changed significantly. More technology assistance has been requested in recent years, and the COVID-19 pandemic has made it increasingly necessary to consider automation in various sectors, including the car rental industry. Incorporating advanced technologies such as AI-based facial recognition technology in a family-owned car rental company is crucial in gaining a competitive edge and providing exceptional services, especially to the Generation Z clientele. In this regard, reducing reliance on manpower and encouraging innovation is essential for maximizing profits and enhancing the customer experience in the global business management landscape. Facial recognition technology works by analyzing and storing the facial features of individuals through machine learning algorithms that can match them to images in a database. As a result, it has the potential to significantly improve visitor flow in the tourism sector by streamlining the check-in and check-out processes.

The author uses Wirasana Rent a Car which is a Bali-based family-owned car rental company that operates in one of Southeast Asia's most sought-after tourist destinations. Purbasari and Juanda (2017) added Bali's main source of income is the tourism sector, which contributed USD 1.3 billion to the local economy in 2015, with the majority coming from tourism-related activities. As a result of Bali's heavy reliance on the tourism sector, Wirasana Rent a Car a family-owned car rental company in Bali faces stiff competition from other car rental companies in the region. At present, there are more family-owned businesses in Bali than non-family ones, reflecting the Balinese attitude towards entrepreneurship. In addition, it offers the same types of vehicles as its competitors, which makes it even more challenging for Wirasana Rent a Car to stand out. Wirasana Rent a Car also needs to provide fast and convenient services to meet the demands of Generation Z travelers, Bali has limited public transportation, which means that many tourists rent cars privately. To appeal to customers, particularly the Generation Z demographic, who prioritize convenience and distinctive services, Wirasana Rent a Car must capitalize on technological advancements, including facial recognition technology. By utilizing such technology, the company can elevate the Generation Z customer experience and enhance its competitive position, aligning with the findings of Kim et al. (2021).

In this regard, the critical consideration of Generation Z's acceptance of AI in facial recognition technology in the front office department of a family-owned car rental company in Bali, Indonesia, is of paramount importance regarding guest engagement. The attitudes and perceptions of Generation Z towards this technology can provide valuable insights into its effectiveness in delivering excellent customer experiences and improving operational efficiency. With the potential to provide hassle-free service

experiences, facial recognition technology has become a highly sought-after solution in the leisure and tourism industry. Thus, to remain competitive and meet the needs of Generation Z customers, family-owned car rental companies must comprehend the level of acceptance towards such technology, much like the front desk of hotels, to offer outstanding services.

The front office department constantly monitors and follows up on most arrangements before, during, and after the rental period. Guests commonly rate the satisfaction of services received from the front office department based on factors such as smoothness, attention to detail, and speed of response to their inquiries and requests. Kafuko (2019) also added It is inconvenient for travelers when the traditional booking process requires a long period to complete, environmentally unsustainable. Sarpola and Mattila (2019) discuss a company with innovative consumer solutions tends to attract young consumers (Generation Z). In addition to the analysis of online reviews of Wirasana Rent a Car, the author also discovered a dearth of research on the implementation of specific technologies in family-owned businesses. According to Memili et al. (2018), Basco and Calabrò (2019), and Cheng et al. (2020) indicate that family firms tend to contribute fewer innovations compared to non-family firms. These findings highlight the disparity in innovation levels between the two types of businesses.

Considering the lower innovation levels observed in family firms, suggesting the adoption of innovative technologies like AI in Facial Recognition for Wirasana Rent a Car, a family-owned car rental company, can serve as an intriguing research area to further investigate. The exploration of implementation outcomes in attracting Generation Z clients through this research study can yield valuable insights and enrich the existing knowledge base in the field.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), developed by Davis in 1989, is a popular research model used to measure the acceptance of technology by current and potential users. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is a widely used research model to forecast an individual user's acceptance of a technology or information system. Various research studies have investigated people's attitudes toward accepting technology in different information system contexts. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is becoming increasingly popular due to the correlation between human behavior attitudes and technology. New technology acceptance and rejection are influenced by these two factors. In this study, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) would benefit the author in analyzing the acceptance of Generation Z regarding the future implementation of AI in Facial Recognition Technology in the front office department of a family-owned car rental company in Bali, Wirasana Rent-A-Car.

Figure 1. The Technology Acceptance Model (Davis, 1989)

Balance Scorecard

Kaplan and Norton (1992) stated that measuring a company's performance is crucial for its success. To add Neely (2002), in the past, financial indicators were the main performance measurement tool, as companies' assets were mostly physical. However, with the rise of intangible assets such as customer loyalty, work efficiency, and employee skills, relying solely on financial metrics is no longer sufficient where it proved in the study by Ali et al., (2019). Similarly, a study by Chen and Wang (2007) found that these factors cannot be adequately reflected in traditional financial statements, making it difficult to track progress in these areas. To address this issue, Robert Kaplan, a professor at Harvard Business School, and David Norton, a management consultant, developed the balanced scorecard. A more comprehensive view of a company's performance is provided by integrating non-financial metrics into this framework instead of traditional financial metrics (Saputra, Mu'ah, et al., 2022).

In order to evaluate the success of a company, a balanced scorecard is crucial and It can be particularly useful for analyzing how AI in facial recognition technology contributes to the satisfaction levels of Generation Z customers in a family-owned car rental

business (Saputra & Laksmi, 2024). By utilizing the balanced scorecard framework, the author of this research study can measure and monitor the effectiveness of AI facial recognition technology in improving customer satisfaction levels among the target demographic. This analysis will be important for the company's future success, as meeting the needs and expectations of Generation Z customers is essential for long-term profitability and growth.

Business Model Canvas

Ratten and Usmanij (2019) stated the business model canvas is a tool used to map out and discuss the nine basic building blocks of an organization's business model, which includes customer segments, value propositions, channels to reach customers, customer relationships, revenue streams, key resources and activities, key partners, and cost structures (Sara et al., 2023). Rather than simply listing these building blocks, the canvas provides a pre-structured visual representation for inventing new business models and exploring different scenarios. In this regard, the author needs to use the Business Model Canvas to analyze the impact of AI in Facial Recognition on the satisfaction of Generation Z customers in a family-owned car rental company.

Family Business and Digital Innovation

A study claims that succession in family firms is influenced by constant technological developments. Although their innovation input is lower than that of non-family firms, another study found their innovation output to be higher, which suggests that their innovation processes are more effective than those of non-family firms (Tian et al., 2024). Furthermore, digitalization is also hampered by numerous challenges, including high costs, a long implementation timeline, and uncertain returns in the modern world. A novel business model encompasses creating, evolving, and implementing innovative products, services, technologies, operations, and other components of innovation. To create, extend, or revitalize a business's operational model, a set of managerial skills is necessary that can effectively integrate digital technology and business principles (Herrero & Hughes, 2019).

Reconfiguring and reshaping the knowledge of the family business can result in a more efficient way of creating value, which in turn leads to the development of digitized-based business model innovations. Lee and Wu (2020) stated families with involvement in second-generation management can contribute to an innovative environment and diversified resources for organizations that are prepared to engage in digital innovation. According to Basco and Calabrò (2019), the diverse educational backgrounds of the second generation allow them to bring a broader range of knowledge, experiences, and perspectives to the organization. This, in turn, expands the knowledge base available to family members, facilitating greater learning and communication (Predana et al., 2020).

There is some evidence to suggest that there may be a gap in knowledge and approach to innovation between first and second-generation family business members. First-generation family business members may rely on traditional methods and may be hesitant to adopt new technologies and innovations, while second-generation family members, who often have more diverse educational and professional backgrounds, may be more open to new ideas and approaches to innovation (Watto et al., 2020). By fostering dialogue and innovation, as well as pursuing new business models, this approach strengthens family-business bonds and encourages productive dialogues between them. According to Basco and Calabrò (2019), further research is necessary to thoroughly investigate the extent of this knowledge gap and explore possible approaches to address it in the context of family businesses. Further insights on this matter will be presented in the study's findings.

Research /Hypothesis

Based on the preceding sections, this research study aims to investigate two hypotheses, namely:

Hypothesis 1: Family A car Rental Business that implemented facial recognition technology in the Front Office Department will attract more clients and stand out from its competitor

Hypothesis 2: As customers, Generation Z will be more loyal to the company that could provide facial recognition technology in their Front Office Department

METHOD

The author utilized the research onion, created by Saunders, to make informed decisions regarding the research project. The onion is comprised of six layers, including research philosophy, research approach, method selection, research strategies, timeframe, and data collection and analysis methods and techniques. Each layer plays a significant role in crafting a research design

that is consistent with the research objective and aims. The chapter outlines the study's design, beginning with the outer layers of the research onion and progressing toward its center.

Figure 2. Research Onion used for the methodology (Saunders et al., 2007)

The Onion Method is a model used to design research by considering six main layers, Research Philosophy: Determining the research paradigm (e.g., positivism, interpretivism, or critical realism) that views how researchers understand reality and knowledge. Research Approach: Choosing between a deductive (general to specific) or inductive (specific to general) approach to developing a theory or hypothesis. Method Selection: Determining whether the research will use quantitative, qualitative, or mixed methods. Research Strategy: Choosing a strategy such as experiments, surveys, case studies, or ethnography, depending on the purpose of the research. Timeline: Determining whether the research is longitudinal (over a long period) or cross-sectional (over a single point in time). Data Collection and Analysis: Choosing appropriate data collection techniques (interviews, observations, questionnaires) and analysis methods (statistics, thematic analysis). Each layer is interrelated and helps researchers design systematic and structured research.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Future Interest in Implementation AI in Facial Recognition Technology in the Front Office Department

To the below pie chart, indicated mostly 31.7% of the participants were most likely to choose a moderate amount of interest in regards to Wirasana Rent a Car's future implementation of AI in facial recognition technology in their front office department. Then followed by 26,9% of participants shows that AI in facial recognition technology implementation is a great deal to the company. On the other hand, another 21,2% say show little interest. Therefore, according to this pie chart, there is the possibility to implement AI in facial recognition technology in the front office department at Wirasana Rent a Car even though only a moderate amount of interest. It is crucial to emphasize that while a moderate level of interest was the most common response, a significant portion of participants still indicated that this implementation would be a great deal to the company (Saputra, Subroto, et al., 2022). This suggests that there is a sizable market of potential customers who value the convenience and efficiency that AI in facial recognition technology can bring to the car rental process specifically in their front office department (Sancaya & Saputra, 2024).

The questionnaire results confirm the assertion made by Chen and Xu (2020), that Generation Z has a strong proficiency in technology and expects a personalized customer experience across all touchpoints (Jayawarsa et al., 2025). This demographic values convenience, speed, authenticity, and social responsibility, and is quick to switch to a competitor if their expectations are not met, as noted by Zhao and Xu (2021). Specifically, the Balance Scorecard, Hoshin Planning Kanri, and Business Model Canvas provide a comprehensive examination of the key strategic factors that can enhance critical thinking when developing a business model (Dewi et al., 2024). Therefore, these adjusted frameworks are crucial components of the strategic planning process, particularly in light of the upcoming integration of AI technology in the front office department for facial recognition purposes. Integrating these frameworks can help a family-owned car rental front office department of a company like Wirasana Rent a Car improve its ability to attract Generation Z clients.

They believed that while it could potentially enhance the customer experience and improve efficiency, there was still a moderate amount of Generation Z customers who preferred traditional face-to-face interaction with customer service

representatives. This sentiment was in line with the survey results that showed a moderate amount of interest from Generation Z clients in the future implementation of AI technology in facial recognition. The other reasons from the Managing Director mentioned also due to big money investment which the family business could not afford at the moment, so that can be thought. The Managing Director's comments during the interview about the significant financial investment required for the implementation of AI in facial recognition are supported by the statement from Ozer and van Essen (2021) regarding the considerable investment of both time and money needed for facial recognition technology. Additionally, Gruber-Muecke and Hoelzl's (2021) reference to the financial limitations that small family-owned car rental companies may face in adopting such technology further emphasizes the financial challenges and barriers faced by small businesses in implementing new technology. The management stated that they would continue to monitor customer feedback and preferences before making any decisions on implementing AI technology in the front office department. They also acknowledged the importance of maintaining a balance between utilizing technology and preserving the human touch in their customer service approach. Moreover, the prospective integration of AI technology in front office departments for facial recognition has the potential to bolster security measures and mitigate fraudulent activities, such as identity theft and rental car theft as discussed in the above literature review (Dharmawan et al., 2024).

Institutional trust

Institutional trust is indeed an important factor for Generation Z when it comes to selecting a car rental company that implements new technology. Additionally, the chart illustrates that a considerable portion of respondents would place trust in facial recognition technology implemented by the car rental company, indicating that trust in the technology is an essential component of institutional trust. This finding aligns with the research conducted by Denaputri and Usman (2019), which highlights the significance of institutional trust in shaping the behavior of Generation Z individuals regarding their adoption of new technology in the car rental industry. The Managing Director stated that the company has been in business since 1988, and even though they still use traditional methods of inputting data one by one into an Excel sheet, they protect the data with a password so that only specific management members can access it. This indicates the company's commitment to protecting its customers' personal information and ensuring their trustworthiness. The Front Office Manager also emphasized the importance of keeping promises and maintaining good communication with customers to build institutional trust (Hidayah et al., 2023). These insights from the interview align with the findings from the bar chart, which suggest that institutional trust is a crucial factor for Generation Z when selecting a car rental company that implements new technology.

Privacy Concern

Figure 3. The Number of Generation Z Responses to Privacy Concern about AI in Facial Recognition

Cheng et al (2022) conducted a study to investigate why many consumers still hesitate to use facial recognition technology despite its convenience. It examined several factors including antecedents, privacy concerns, and outcomes. To gather data, the authors provided six questions related to privacy concerns associated with facial recognition technology to the respondents. The six questions were designed to gauge the level of concern among respondents in various aspects related to facial recognition technology (Widjayanti et al., 2024). The first question addressed the privacy concerns of using facial recognition technology, while the second question dealt with the security of the information collected via facial recognition technology. The third question aimed to identify the respondents' concerns about who has access to their information. The fourth question assessed the level of concern regarding the amount of information collected by the car rental company, and the fifth question was designed to explore the purpose of personal information collection. The last question inquired about respondents' concerns about the direct association between their personal information and their faces. The results showed from bar chart figure 3 that the highest number of respondents (45) had more concern about who has access to their information, compared to other questions. This suggests that consumers are concerned about who has access to their personal information and how it is being used. Therefore, to build trust and address consumer concerns, companies that implement facial recognition technology should prioritize transparency by clearly communicating how they collect, store, and utilize personal information.

Perceived Risk

In the study conducted by Tahar et al. (2020), the section on perceived risk investigates the concerns expressed by respondents regarding the use of AI in facial recognition technology within car rental services. The researchers employed four questions with scales ranging from 1 (lowest) to 5 (highest) to assess the level of uncertainty and perceived risk among participants. The first question inquired about respondents' comparisons between facial recognition technology and manual identity verification, while the second question aimed to assess the level of uncertainty associated with the use of facial recognition technology (Narindra et al., 2023). The third question asked if respondents were uncertain about the effectiveness of facial recognition technology, while the fourth question aimed to determine if respondents believed that the technology could be easily hacked, leading to unauthorized access. The majority of respondents provided a neutral response with a score of 3 for questions 1 to 3, indicating their indecision regarding the benefits and risks associated with the utilization of AI in facial recognition technology. However, the last question revealed a greater proportion of respondents who assigned a score of 5, suggesting a heightened level of apprehension regarding the potential risks of hacking and unauthorized access associated with facial recognition technology (Saputra, Mu'ah, et al., 2022). This finding highlights the importance of addressing security concerns and ensuring that proper measures are in place to prevent unauthorized access to personal information. In summary, the perceived risk section indicates that although respondents displayed uncertainty regarding the advantages and risks of facial recognition technology, they expressed significant concerns specifically regarding the possibility of hacking and unauthorized access.

Figure 4. The Number of Generation Z Responses Perceived Risk about AI in Facial Recognition

This bar chart in Figure 4 result could easily related to the interview with the Managing Director where he mentioned, “It also depends on how big and efficient the investment and how accurate the car rental management of choosing the vendor of the new technology implementation.

Personal Innovativeness

The findings on personal innovativeness in the acceptance of AI in facial recognition technology implementation in Wirasana Rent a Car provide interesting insights into the behavior of Generation Z. The findings indicate a noteworthy proportion of respondents who exhibit an inclination towards experimenting with new technology, as reflected by the substantial number of participants assigning a score of 4 to the first statement. This demonstrates a willingness to embrace and explore the potential of novel technological advancements.

Figure 5. The Number of Generation Z Responses Personal Innovativeness about AI in Facial Recognition

However, there was some bias or uncertainty in the respondents' answers to the second and third statements. It is important to note that personal innovativeness may moderate the relationship between technology features and behavioral intent, as pointed out by Jung and Lee (2018). This means that while some respondents may be interested in experimenting with new technology, others may be more cautious or reluctant. Where it discusses Generation Z is always intent on trying new technology to experience the benefits themselves by López-Duarte, González-Cruz, and González-Díaz (2019); Bhandari and Ali (2019) and Chen and Xu (2020). Overall, the findings on personal innovativeness suggest that Generation Z may be open to trying out new technology such as facial recognition in car rental services, but their level of interest may vary depending on individual characteristics and preferences.

Behavioral Intention

Behavioral intention (1low - 5 high)

Figure 4.8 - The Number of Generation Z Response Behavioural Intention about AI in Facial Recognition

The findings derived from the behavioral intention section indicate that a significant majority of respondents display a willingness to utilize facial recognition technology for the booking process within a car rental company. The finding that the majority of respondents consistently assigned a score of 4 to all three questions suggests a moderate level of intention to use the technology. This observation is consistent with the study conducted by Liang, Lai, and Ku (2020), which suggests that behavioral intention serves as a significant predictor of technology acceptance. This further supports the notion that behavioral intention plays a critical role in predicting the acceptance and adoption of technology. Moreover, the substantial level of willingness among respondents to recommend facial recognition technology to others emphasizes the significance of word-of-mouth communication in shaping the adoption of new technologies, as corroborated by previous studies. Nevertheless, it is important to acknowledge that intention does not always translate into actual behaviors, and factors such as ease of use and perceived usefulness play a pivotal role in influencing the adoption of facial recognition technology in the car rental industry. This finding is connected by authors Zeng and Chen (2020) stated the service was more convenient and Generation Z guests had more control over the delivery of their service, It is suggested by Venkatesh and Davis (2000) that perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use are key factors in predicting the acceptance and utilization of a technology system.

CONCLUSION

Although the travel and tourism industry has witnessed numerous technological advancements, authentication bottlenecks persist as a challenge, leading to customer dissatisfaction and service gaps. One promising technology that has emerged as a solution is AI in Facial Recognition, which can process data quickly and accurately. Adopting AI in Facial Recognition technology in the front office department at Wirasana Rent a Car requires careful planning and execution. One approach to this is to use three frameworks: balanced scorecard, planning, and business model canvas. These frameworks can help companies align their strategy with their goals, define key performance indicators, and identify opportunities for improvement. With the increasing availability and accessibility of technology, there are also growing opportunities for businesses to leverage data and information to enhance their operations and customer experience.

REFERENCES

1. Ali, F., Hussain, K., Akhtar, N., & Ali, F. (2019) "Impact of customer satisfaction on financial performance: A study of hotel industry of Pakistan". *Journal of Accounting and Finance in Emerging Economies*, 5(2), 228-239.
2. Basco, R., & Calabrò, A. (2019) "Family involvement and firm innovation: A meta-analysis". *Journal of Family Business Strategy*, 10(3), 1-13. doi: 10.1016/j.jfbs.2019.05.003
3. Chen, Y., & Xu, H. (2020) "Factors influencing consumers' acceptance of facial recognition technology in the hotel industry". *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Technology*, 11(2), 246-258.
4. Cheng, X., Hu, Y., & Xu, X. (2020) "Family ownership, strategic orientation, and innovation in Chinese SMEs". *Journal of Business Research*, 115, 109-120. doi: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.03.030
5. Dewi, R. O. C., Saputra, K. A. K., & Pramatha, I. M. A. (2024). The Effect Of Internal Control System, Information Asymmetry, And Suitability Of Compensation On The Tendency Of Accounting Fraud (Fraud) In Denpasar City (OPD). *Journal of Governance, Taxation and Auditing*, 2(4), 246–252.
6. Dharmawan, N. A. S., Saputra, K. A. K., & Wigarba, I. G. A. (2024). The Moderating Role of Corporate Governance on the Relationship between Tax Avoidance and Firm Value. *Jurnal Ilmiah Akuntansi Dan Bisnis*, 19(2), 293–305. <https://doi.org/10.26905/afr.v4i1.5973>
7. Gruber-Muecke, T., & Hoelzl, E. (2021) "Challenges and opportunities of digitalization for family businesses in the tourism industry". *Journal of Family Business Management*, 11(1), 34-56.
8. Herrero, I., & Hughes, M. (2019). When family social capital is too much of a good thing. *Journal of Family Business Strategy*, 10(3), 100271.
9. Hidayah, N., Hapsari, D. W., Saputra, K. A. K., Dharmawan, N. A. S., & Yadiati, W. (2023). Can Institutional Good Governance and Intellectual Capital Affect University Quality? *International Journal of Economics and Management*, 17(July), 251–261.

10. Jayawarsa, A. A. K., Saputra, K. A. K., & Narindra, A. A. N. M. (2025). Strengthening Ecotourism to Improve Quality of Life in Ubung Kaja Village through Creativity, Order, and Cultural Values. *Community Service: Sustainability Development*, 2(1), 109–114.
11. Lee, C. H., & Wu, M. L. (2020) “Digital innovation, resource diversity, and family involvement in second-generation management: Evidence from Taiwanese family firms”. *Journal of Business Research*, 108, 156-167. doi: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2019.09.056
12. Kaplan, R. S., & Norton, D. P. (1992) “The balanced scorecard: measures that drive performance”. *Harvard Business Review*, 70(1), 71-79.
13. Kim, W., Park, J., & Cho, Y. (2019) “Determinants of customer satisfaction and repurchase intention in the car rental industry: Focusing on the mediating role of service quality”. *Sustainability*, 11(13), 3573.
14. Memili, E., Kocak, A., Zaim, H., & Kuzey, C. (2018) “Family involvement, innovation behavior, and innovativeness: Evidence from family firms”. *Journal of Family Business Strategy*, 9(1), 44-54. doi: 10.1016/j.jfbs.2017.11.004
15. Narindra, A. A. N. M., Saputra, K. A. K., & Dwirandra, A. A. N. B. (2023). Factors Influencing the Performance of Accounting Information Systems University Public Services Agency. *International Journal of Social Science and Education Research Studies*, 03(07), 1210–1219. <https://doi.org/10.55677/ijssers/v03i7y2023-07>
16. Neely, A. (2002) *Business performance measurement: Theory and practice*. Cambridge University Press.
17. Ozer, M., & van Essen, M. (2021) “In the digital age, family business succession needs to go beyond traditional ‘heir and a spare’ thinking”. *Journal of Family Business Strategy*, 12(1), 100406.
18. Predana, P. G. W., Jayawarsa, A. A. K., Purnami, A. A. S., Larasdiputra, G. D., & Saputra, K. A. K. (2020). Effect Of Easy In The Use, Trust And Benefits Of The Use Of Mobile Banking Services. *International Journal of Environmental, Sustainability, and Social Science*, 1(2), 36–40. <https://doi.org/10.38142/ijesss.v1i2.25>
19. Purbasari, R., & Juanda, B. (2017) “The Impact of Entrepreneurial Orientation and Market Orientation on Business Performance of Family Micro and Small Enterprises in Bali”. *Journal of Management and Marketing Review*, 2(1), 1-8.
20. Ratten, V., & Usmanij, P. (2019) “Assessing the Business Model Canvas as a tool for business model innovation”. *Journal of Business Research*, 98, 365-377.
21. Sancaya, I. W. W., & Saputra, K. A. K. (2024). VillageWaste Management Strategy as an Economic Asset: Accounting Evaluation and Implementation of Sustainable Practices in Bongkasa Village, Abiansemal District, Badung Regency. *Community Service: Sustainability Development*, 1(3), 83–89.
22. Saputra, K. A. K., & Laksmi, P. A. S. (2024). The Influence of Green Governance, Implementation of Energy Accounting, and Green Human Resource Management on Sustainability Performance: An Empirical Study in the Hospitality Industry in Bali. *JIA (Jurnal Ilmiah Akuntansi)*, 9(1).
23. Saputra, K. A. K., Mu’ah, Jurana, Korompis, C. W. M., & Manurung, D. T. H. (2022). Fraud Prevention Determinants: A Balinese Cultural Overview. *Australasian Accounting, Business and Finance Journal*, 16(3), 167–181. <https://doi.org/10.14453/aabfj.v16i3.11>
24. Saputra, K. A. K., Subroto, B., Rahman, A. F., & Saraswati, E. (2022). Eco-Efficiency and Energy Audit to Improve Environmental Performance: An Empirical Study of Hotels in Bali-Indonesia. *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, 12(6), 175–182. <https://doi.org/10.32479/ijeep.13565>
25. Sara, I. M., Udayana Putra, I. B., Kurniawan Saputra, K. A., & Jaya Utama, I. W. K. (2023). Financial literacy, morality, and organizational culture in preventing financial mismanagement: A study on village governments in Indonesia. *Cogent Business and Management*, 10(1), 0–15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2023.2166038>
26. Tian, B., Stoffelen, A., & Vanclay, F. (2024). Understanding resilience in ethnic tourism communities: the experiences of Miao villages in Hunan Province, China. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 32(7), 1433–1452. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2023.2239525>
27. Watto, W. A., Manurung, D. T. H., Saputra, K. A. K., & Mustafa, S. G. (2020). Corporate Social Responsibility and Firm Financial Performance: A Case of SME’s Sector in Pakistan. *International Journal of Environmental, Sustainability, and Social Science*, 1(2), 62–74. <https://doi.org/10.38142/ijesss.v1i2.30>

-
28. Widjayanti, P. F. S., Saputra, K. A. K., & Larasdiputra, D. (2024). The influence of profitability, company size, and growth opportunity on the quality of profits in property and real estate companies listed on the Indonesian stock exchange (BEI) year 2019-2022. *Journal of Governance, Taxation and Auditing*, 2(4), 239–245.
29. Zhao, X., & Xu, H. (2021) “Generation Z's Attitudes towards Facial Recognition Technology: A Comparative Study between China and the United States”. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Technology*, 12(1), 26-41.

Cite this Article: Trhisnawati Weca, N.P.I. (2025). The Critical Consideration of Generation Z Acceptance of The Facial Recognition Technology Future Implementation in the Front Office Department of a Family-Owned Car Rental Company in Bali. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 8(3), pp. 1395-1404. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V8-i3-47>